

BBioNets

Boosting the adoption
of Bio-Based Technologies

DELIVERABLE D1.4

Report on the validation and prioritisation of BBTs per region

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Table of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
AD	Anaerobic Digestion/digester
D	Deliverable
ETR	European Transnational Region
EU	European Union
FAN	Forestry and Agricultural Network
GA	Grant Agreement
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
kW	Kilowatt
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
RPFA	Regional Partners for Forestry and Agriculture
RR	Represented Region
WP	Work Package

1 Executive Summary

This report summarises the outcomes of the T1.3 workshop, titled “Validation and Prioritisation of Bio-Based Technologies (BBTs) per Region”, conducted with FANs (Forestry and Agricultural Networks) from each Represented Region (RR). Aligned with the BBioNets grant agreement (GA), this workshop forms a crucial step in validating and refining the early prioritisation of BBTs identified in the BBioNets Assessment Tool (D2.2) and mapped through European initiatives in T2.1 “BBioNets Inventory and Knowledge Collection” alongside the information collected by partners in the D2.4 Report on the high-level study of regional dynamics. The insights documented in this report D1.4 are intended to enhance the BBT Assessment Tool (D2.3) and, ultimately the D2.5 Roadmap for BBTs implementation.

The workshop served three primary objectives:

- (i) **Validation and Feasibility Assessment:** In a follow-up workshop, BBioNets project partners in each RR met with the FAN members in their region. FAN members reviewed the early prioritisation of BBTs, assessing their feasibility and relevance for their respective regions based on local resources, needs, and regional challenges identified in the preceding “Resources and Needs Workshop” (meeting No.2).
- (ii) **Recalibration and Information Gathering:** New information was collected to align with updated inventory fields in T2.1. This process refined BBT parameters and generated weighted variables for the assessment tool.
- (iii) **Promotion of European Transnational Regions (ETR) Meetings:** The workshop also laid the groundwork for upcoming ETR meetings, held in December 2024.

The discussions and decisions from these workshops are captured in this report captures, providing region-specific validation of BBTs, prioritisation outcomes, and recalibrated needs and resources. These insights contribute to a more tailored and impactful application of bio-based technologies across regions, promoting alignment with EU goals and enhancing regional circularity innovation.

Some of the findings are in a similar trend to the ones of Deliverable 1.5 ‘Identified regional needs and challenges’, i.e., the recalibration of regional needs and resources and the suitability of BBTs to each region aligned strongly with the nature of regional agricultural and forestry strengths.

In **Italy**, the agronomic use of bark and pruning residues was the BBT most aligned with the resources and needs of the region due to its potential for enhancing soil quality and reducing fossil-derived peat dependency. Needs shifted focus to projects that emphasise investment resources and sustainable materials. While biochar and composts were perceived as the most economically valuable resources. There was a focus on the Olive Industry in **Spain**: Technologies related to olive by-products dominated prioritisation, reflecting Andalusia’s agricultural profile, while in terms of needs, these shifted towards financial support and infrastructure readiness. Olive pits and pomace were identified as high-value resources. Similarly, in **Greece** olive-mill by-product recovery technologies (e.g., OLEOVALORIZA) emerged as key technologies while manure was a significant biomass resource. Needs in the region shifted to increase focus on farmer education and demonstration schemes. In the **Czech Republic** 97 stakeholders participated in the FAN workshop to validate technologies like biogas systems and biochar-enhanced compost. In terms of resources, agricultural residues and innovative biomass utilisation was highlighted, as was a greater emphasis on the need for value chain development. In **Ireland**, technologies focusing on soil health and resource efficiency were prioritised, including

composting agricultural residues and utilising mixed biomass for energy and soil enhancement. Regional funding for shared technology and infrastructure emerged as the top priority. Priorities like green biorefineries gained attention for their potential to valorise biomasses, while technologies such as slurry separation remained critical for managing agricultural waste. Finally, in **Poland**, BBTs aligned to the region's needs and resources included emissions control in slurry management, and the enhancement of composting with biochar. While resources remained unchanged, prioritisation of needs shifted with increased focus on forestry resource optimisation and carbon-rich biomass production. Improved machinery for collecting wood biomass and biomass coaling installations rose in priority.

2 Introduction

This document examines the feasibility of OG-identified and locally applied BBTs in each BBioNets consortium region. Data were gathered through workshops with FAN members held in-person, online, or both in each region. It revisits and recalibrates the resources and needs identified in the preliminary workshops of early 2024 (outlined in Deliverable 1.5) to reprioritise them for improved adoption of circular processes in each region.

The report outlines the T1.3 workshops' purpose, key outcomes, and methodology provided to consortium members for data collection. It provides an overview of BBT prioritisation, feasibility analysis, resource recalibration, and ETR framework promotion in each region. It also summarises the debates on BBT feasibility and recalibrated resources/needs, as well as key economic variables such as supply value (€ per tonne of biomass products) and subrogation value (replacement costs of bio-based products vs. traditional fertilisers).

Key highlights of this report include the outcomes for the preliminary top-prioritised BBTs in terms of their alignment and feasibility in each region, regional variations in BBT selection and prioritisation, and the changes in the perceived prioritisation of resources and needs in each RR between these workshops and the preliminary workshops held earlier in 2024.

To conclude, this report provides a comprehensive analysis of the prioritisation, feasibility, and economic implications of regionally relevant BBTs. The findings and recalibrations presented herein aim to support the advancement of circular bioeconomy processes across diverse representative regions within the European Union (EU), ensuring alignment with local needs and resources while fostering the adoption of sustainable bio-based technologies.

3 Section 1 - Methodology guidelines generated.

To obtain all desired outcomes from the meeting No.3 with FANs, the T1.3 Validation and prioritisation of BBTs per region proposed to BBioNets partners to perform a homogenised workshop amongst regions. This workshop, although it was adapted to every region's needs, targeted three main characteristics:

1. Part 1: Debate over the early prioritised BBTs and their feasibility for their region.
2. Part 2: Recalibrate previous information (needs and resources) and obtain new information (new inventory fields for T2.1).
3. Part 3: Promote ETR meeting/ FAN operational framework.

3.1 Part 1: Guidelines to Debate over the BBTs and feasibility for their region.

For partners to debate with their FANs over the BBTs and their feasibility for their respective region:

1. **Partners selected up to 10 BBTs** from the early prioritisation of BBTs in BBT assessment tool that match the region's biomasses. A portfolio of potential BBTs for each region was selected for each FAN. With MTU's help, RPFAs selected 10 BBTs from this portfolio. These BBTs then were given to the FANs to debate and discuss their feasibility to the region. As the BBT Assessment Tool only produces an early prioritisation list, **it was noted that where BBTs were prioritised highly, it was important to manually select those that are adequately matched to the biomass predominant in that region, bearing in mind the outputs of the D2.4.**
2. **Collection of weights** of specific variables for the selected BBTs for the BBT Assessment Tool. To obtain quantitative weights, the suitability and feasibility of specific BBTs was debated over **5 questions** that grouped several variables that the BBT Assessment Tool reads (**Error! Reference source not found.**), and that were associated with a graded arrow system. In other words, each question was paired with one graded arrow that held weights from +5 to -5 (**Error! Reference source not found.**). The 10 BBTs selected were prioritised in each of the arrows giving weights depending on its feasibility to the region i.e., BBTs were ranked according to how they would respond to the questions. Knowing that different BBTs can receive the same weighting under same question, the meaning of the weights in the arrows were interpreted as follows:
 - a. A BBT weighted +5 completely aligns and responds to the question. A BBT weighted from +4 until +1 aligns and responds less than another weighted +5.
 - b. A BBT weighted -5 does not respond nor align at all to the question and the FAN would likely not have it in the region. A BBT weighted from -4 until -1 does not respond or align to the question but it is most likely to be accepted than the one weighted -5.
 - c. A BBT weighted 0 is in between of the two above, it is not as desirable as those weighted positive (+) but is more desirable than those weighted negative (-).
3. Each workshop collected the information from the graded arrow system in the template provided by Teagasc (**Error! Reference source not found.**).

Workshop questions and grouped variables

1. Will the BBT be suitable for the resources available in the region?
 - Variables: Feedstock, Description of BBT, Reference sector, Key word, Categories.
2. Will the BBT be suitable for the needs in the region?
 - Needs/problem statement.
3. Will this BBT have potential to develop a value chain in the region?
 - Potential value chain, Objective, Outcome, Intended user/Final user, Complexity.
4. Economic potential of this BBT for the region
 - Economic potential, Added value.
5. Will this BBT benefit the environment and society of the region?
 - Environmental and social impact and C sequestration.

Figure 3-1. Questions for the feasibility debate over the BBTs in the region and the variables referred under them.

Figure 3-2. Weighting by graded arrows prioritisation of BBT variables using graded arrows.

Table 3-1. Template for the collection of weights from the graded arrow system.

Questions:	Will the BBT be suitable for the resources available in the region?	Will the BBT be suitable for the needs in the region?	Will this BBT have potential to develop a value chain in the region?	Economic potential of this BBT for the region	Will this BBT benefit the environment and society of the region?
<i>Grouped Variables:</i>	<i>Variables: Feedstock, Description of BBT, Reference sector, Key word, Categories.</i>	<i>Needs/problem statement.</i>	<i>Potential value chain, Objective, Outcome, Intended user/Final user, Complexity.</i>	<i>Economic potential, Added value.</i>	<i>Environmental and social impact and C sequestration.</i>
BBT #			Weighting		
BBT 1 Name:	e.g.: +1	e.g.: +5	e.g.: +1
BBT 2 Name:	e.g.: -2	e.g.: 0	e.g.: +1
BBT 3 Name:	e.g.: +1	e.g.: -3	e.g.: +1
BBT 4 Name:
BBT 5 Name:
BBT 6 Name:
BBT 7 Name:
BBT 8 Name:
BBT 9 Name:
BBT10 Name:

3.1.1 Interpretation of weights obtained for the BBT assessment tool

This section delves into how the weights collected in the workshops will be processed by MTU to include them in the BBT Assessment Tool, offering a clearer interpretation of the results obtained. This methodology has been followed as a transformation of the quantitative data attributed to qualitative data in the workshops. As said above, the list of variables evaluated in the workshop was grouped by similarity in 5 questions to simplify the debate with FANs. Two types of variables were selected, variables that are dropdown fields, i.e., **given values** in the T2.1 BBioNets Inventory, and variables that are a **narrative synthesis** in the inventory.

The weights obtained from the **variables that have given values** from the T2.1 BBioNets Inventory were processed following the Equation number 1 (*Eq1*), which looks for an average of the weights given to a specific field of a variable across different BBTs. Therefore, a positive or negative weight will be given to the given value of the variables of the BBTs prioritised.

$$Eq1: \text{Weight of a field of a variable} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n WFVBi + WFVB_{i+1} + \dots + WFVB_n}{n}$$

WFVB = Weight given to a specific field of a variable in a BBT

Example:

BBT 1: Reference sector: A1.6 Support activities to agriculture and post-harvest crop activities. Weight given to the grouped variables where Reference sector is: 3

BBT2: Reference sector: A1.6 Support activities to agriculture and post-harvest crop activities. Weight given to the grouped variables where Reference sector is: 2.

$$\text{Weight of A1.6 Support activities of Reference sector} = \frac{3 + 2}{2} = 2.5$$

Pages 18 to 20 contain the given values of each variable from the BBioNets Inventory, so the reader could visualise the association of the Eq1 to each of the given values.

For the variables that have written text or a narrative synthesis from the T2.1 BBioNets Inventory fields, Equation number 2 (*Eq2*) was generated. There are only 4 variables of this type, Description BBT, Objective, Outcome and Needs.

The *Eq2* works with the prior identification of key words in the narrative text. Weights obtained from the graded arrow system were given to specific key words, accounting for weights from repeated key words. This way, the tool can look for those key words and give higher or lower punctuation to these. It generates an average of the weights given to repeated key words in a variable across different BBTs.

$$Eq2: \text{Weight of a key word of a variable} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n WKWi + WKW_{i+1} + \dots + WKW_n}{n}$$

WKW = Weight Key Word

Example *Eq1*:

BBT #	Variable	Key words	WKW1= Weight in BBT1	WKW2= Weight in BBT2	...	Weight eq2
BB1	Description	Livestock, manure	2	2	...	2
BBT2	Description	Fertiliser	1		...	-1
BBT3	Description	Fertiliser	-3		...	-1

Application of the Eq1 to each of the given values from the BBioNets Inventory

Reference sector	Weight
A1.2 Growing of perennial crops	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
A1.1 Growing of non-perennial crops	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
A1.6 Support activities to agriculture and post-harvest crop activities	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
A1.4 Animal production	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
A1.5 Mixed farming	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
A1.3 Plant propagation	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
A1.7 Hunting, trapping and related service activities	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
A2.3 Gathering of wild growing non-wood products	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
A2.2 Logging	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
A2.4 Support services to forestry	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
A2.1 Silviculture and other forestry activities	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
A3.1 Fishing	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
A3.2 Aquaculture	<i>Weight eq 1</i>

Feedstock	Weight
Biomass	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Biomass residues	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Wastes	<i>Weight eq 1</i>

Categories	Weight
Crop residues and perennial plants F1	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Designer crops for optimised biomass content F2	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Algae biomass F3	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Waste or recycled material FC	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Microbial assisted processing C1	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Biorefineries C2	<i>Weight eq 1</i>

Value chains	Weight
3 - High potential - Significant arisings of feedstocks available currently.	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
2 - Medium potential - Significant availability of feedstocks available by 2035.	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
1- Low potential - Low to medium arisings of feedstock available between 2023-2035	<i>Weight eq 1</i>

Sociological potential	Weight
3 - High potential - Expected to bring at least 3 significant social benefits.	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
2 - Medium potential -Expected to bring 2 or 1 social benefits.	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
1 - Low potential - doesn't bring any social benefits.	<i>Weight eq 1</i>

Key Word	Weight
Agro-ecology	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
AKIS, incl. advice, training, on-farm demo, interactive innovation projects	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Animal husbandry	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Animal welfare	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Aquaculture	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Arable crops	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Biodiversity and nature	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Circular economy, incl. waste, by-products and residues	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Climate change (incl. GHG reduction, adaptation and mitigation, and other air related issues)	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Competitiveness/new business models	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Crop rotation/crop diversification/dual-purpose or mixed cropping	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Digitalisation, incl. data and data technologies	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Energy	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Equipment and machinery	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Farm diversification	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Fodder and feed	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Food security, safety, quality, processing and nutrition	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Forestry	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Genetic resources	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Greenhouse crops	<i>Weight eq 1</i>

Landscape/land management	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Organic farming	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Outdoor horticulture and woody crops (incl. viticulture, olives, fruit, ornamentals)	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Pest/disease control in animals	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Pest/disease control in plants	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Plant nutrients	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Rural issues	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Social innovation	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Soil	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Supply chain, marketing and consumption	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Water	<i>Weight eq 1</i>

Environmental benefits	Weight
3 - High potential - Expected to bring at least 3 significant environmental benefits.	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
2 - Medium potential - Expected to bring 2 or 1 environmental benefits.	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
1 - Low potential - doesn't bring any environmental benefits.	<i>Weight eq 1</i>

C Sequestration	Weight
3 - High potential - strong potential for carbon sequestration at the feedstock and product level).	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
2 - Medium potential - strong potential for carbon sequestration at the feedstock or product level only.	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
1 - Low potential - low potential for carbon sequestration	<i>Weight eq 1</i>

Economic potential	Weight
3 - High potential - Expected to bring at least 3 significant economic benefits.	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
2 - Medium potential - Expected to bring 2 or 1 economic benefits.	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
1 - Low potential - doesn't bring any economic benefits.	<i>Weight eq 1</i>

Added value	Weight
Energy & Heat = Very low	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Bulk Chemicals & Fuels = Low	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Bioplastics & Polymers = Intermediate	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Food/Feed = High	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Fine chemicals = Very high	<i>Weight eq 1</i>

Final user	Weight
Farmer	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Forester	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Advisor	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Researcher	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
NGO (env, climate...)	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Training organization	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Processor or retailer	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Consumer	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Public Authority	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
Other	<i>Weight eq 1</i>

Complexity	Weight
'1 - very easy to use/replicate	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
2 -easy to use /replicate	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
3 -complex application	<i>Weight eq 1</i>
4 - very complex application (conditions)	<i>Weight eq 1</i>

3.2 Part 2: Guidelines to Recalibrate previous information and obtain new information

After completion of Part 1 of the workshop, FANs had a more accurate vision of what BBioNets is aiming to bring to the region. Two activities were performed in the part 2 of the workshop:

1. **Review and update of the Needs and Resources available in the region stated in T1.2.** The list of needs stated in T1.2 were reviewed, and new ones were added if deemed necessary. A reviewed prioritisation of these were also made. Similar approach was taken for the list of resources stated in T1.2. RPFAs were given flexibility on the methodology to follow to collect this information. Methodologies such as dot voting or the use of Mentimeter were suggested. At the end of the event, RPFAs generated an updated prioritised list of needs and resources, see Error! Reference source not found..

Table 3-2. Updated table of needs and resources.

Needs (revised in workshop T1.3)	Resources (revised in workshop T1.3)
1.	1.
2.	2.
3.	3.
...	...

2. **Collection of information to match the two new inventory fields CREA is generating for economic variables; hence new questions were needed to be asked to the FANs.** This information was collected in the Error! Reference source not found.-3.
 - a. First field: **Supply Value.** This new field in the T2.1 addresses an estimate of the price that the bio-based technology owner would pay to buy the Bio inputs. This can be expressed in the T1.3 workshop as how much farmers and foresters has been paid in the past for biomasses (non-food) that processors valorise.
 - b. Second field: **Subrogation value.** This other new field addresses the price of a replacement product (e.g., price of a biofertiliser vs current fertiliser). This can be expressed in the T1.3 workshop as bio-based products' prices farmers and foresters have seen/used/are aware of.

Table 3-3. Supply and subrogation value obtained in the T1.3 workshop.

Supply Value	Subrogation value
Biomass 1: €/kg	Bio-based product 1: €
Biomass 2: €/kg	Bio-based product 2: €
...	...

3.3 Part 3: Guidelines to promote ETR meeting/ FAN Operational framework

Promotion of the European Transnational Regions (ETR) meetings was a vital component of the FAN workshop at the time, ensuring achieving engagement and collaboration among stakeholders. As the ETR meetings aim to foster cross-regional dialogue, share best practices, and enhance the adoption of BBTs across regions, RPFAs made sure to communicate that BBioNets were going to start these cross-fertilisation meetings. This strategy was key to maximise participation and generating interest among FAN members and other stakeholders.

Section 2: Workshop Results

This section discusses the results of the workshops held by the FAN in each region of the BBioNets Consortium. The details of the workshop, its format and structure are provided. This section discusses the results of the prioritisation of BBTs per region followed by the recalibration of resources and needs in each region from the results of previous workshops. Finally, economic variables relating to supply and subrogation values are provided.

4 Italian FAN

4.1 Workshop details

Table 4-1. Details of workshop 3 in the Italian FAN

Venue	Terra Madre meeting
Date	30/09/2024
Format	In person
Attendee number	9
Name of the event	<i>The available resources and needs to be met from a circular economy perspective: BBT Prioritization and Needs.</i>

4.2 Section 1: Debate over the BBTs and feasibility for their region.

During the first phase of the workshop, 10 BBTs were introduced to the FAN members by CREA team. These BBTs were taken from EU Operational Groups and presented to FAN members for debate in order to discuss their feasibility for their RR. These BBTs are displayed in Table 4-2:

Table 4-2. Description of BBTs selected for debate among FAN members for their suitability to the Italian region.

No.	BBT Code	BBT Description
1	IT54-ProBEST	Agronomic use of bark and pruning residues to increase organic carbon in agricultural soils, offering an alternative to fossil-derived peat.
2	ES-Biochar/BIOCH	Use of prunings for biochar production.
3	ES/TOMATO GROUP	Utilization of tomato by-products.
4	ΕΛΑΙΩΝΑΣ	Composting of olive residues.
5	OLIHERB	Production of natural infusions and food additives from olive leaves (rich in polyphenols and other bioactive ingredients).
6	SWANFOAM	Transformation of agricultural biomass residues into compost or fertilizers.
7	MIXBIOPELLS/PLTIZ	Pelletizing mixed biomass residues and waste from agriculture and forestry.
8	IT45-Stabilized Litter	Stabilized bedding for dairy cows: optimizing the use of bedding derived from the solid fraction of separated manure.
9	Innovative Rice Residue Management Practices	A method for managing rice residues within the context of sustainable and innovative agricultural practices.
10	GO_GRASS	Conversion of low-quality grass from wetlands into biochar to improve soil quality.

4.2.1 Results on the prioritisation of BBTs in the region

The Italian FAN evaluated the list of BBTs outlined in Table 4-2 above to assess their suitability for the region, with weightage scores reflecting their alignment with regional needs and challenges. The weightage score obtained for each BBT by FAN members for each of the 5 questions outlined above are displayed below in Table 4-3. Among the technologies, BBT 1 (agronomic use of bark and pruning residues to increase organic carbon in soils) received the highest score of 3.8. This highlights its potential to enhance soil quality while providing a sustainable alternative to fossil-derived peat. Other well-received technologies include BBT 5 (production of natural infusions and food additives from olive leaves) with a score of 2.8, and BBTs 6 and 7 (transformation of agricultural biomass into compost/fertilizers and pelletizing mixed biomass residues), both scoring 2.7, indicating strong

support for technologies focused on value addition and waste transformation. Conversely, BBT 10 (conversion of low-quality grass from wetlands into biochar) and BBT 2 (use of prunings for biochar production) were deemed less suitable, receiving negative scores of -3.7 and -2.9 respectively. This suggests that biochar-related technologies may face challenges in feasibility or alignment with regional priorities. Overall, the findings underscore the Italian FAN's preference for technologies that promote soil health, resource efficiency, and value addition in agriculture.

Table 4-3. Summary of the prioritisation of each BBT for each key question

Questions	Is the BBT suitable for the available resources in the region?	Is the BBT suitable for the region's needs?	Does this BBT have the potential to develop a value chain?	Economic potential of the BBT for the region	Will the BBT benefit the environment and society in the region?	Weighting (average)
BBT 1	4.5	4.5	3	2	5	3.8
BBT 2	-3	-3	-3.5	-3.5	-1.5	-2.9
BBT 3	0.5	1	0.5	0	1	0.6
BBT 4	2.5	2.5	2.5	2	2.5	2.4
BBT 5	2	3	3	3	3	2.8
BBT 6	4	4	1.5	1.5	2.5	2.7
BBT 7	3	3	2.5	2	3	2.7
BBT 8	2	2.5	1.5	0.5	1	1.5
BBT 9	3.5	3	1.5	2	2	2.4
BBT10	-4.5	-4	-4	-3	-3	-3.7

4.3 Section 2: Recalibration of Needs and Resources for the region

4.3.1 Recalibration of resources in the region

Table 4-4 presents a list of biomass resources identified in the Italian region, initially outlined in a meeting held on 18/04/2024 and later revisited and recalibrated during a follow-up meeting on 30/09/2024. Interestingly, the rankings and inclusion of resources remained consistent across both meetings, reflecting an overall agreement on the relative importance and availability of these resources.

Table 4-4. Results on the calibration of resources available in the Italian RR

Resources meeting 18/04/2024	Resources meeting 30/09/2024
1. Treated wastewater	1. Treated wastewater
2. chestnut shavings	2. chestnut shavings
3. Forest resources	3. Forest resources
4. Woody pruning waste	4. Woody pruning waste
5. Crops pruning waste	5. Crops pruning waste
6. Olive mill wastewater	6. Olive mill wastewater
7. Spent substrates	7. Spent substrates
8. Agri-food waste	8. Agri-food waste
9. Olive pomace	9. Olive pomace
10. Uncultivated lands	10. Uncultivated lands
11. Grape pomace	11. Grape pomace
12. Manure	12. Manure
13. Whey	13. Whey
14. Male calves from dairy farms (dual-purpose breed) that are sent to slaughter in the Netherlands. despite the potential to create a local value chain.	14. Male calves from dairy farms (dual-purpose breed) that are sent to slaughter in the Netherlands. despite the potential to create a local value chain.

4.3.2 Recalibration of needs in the region

There were a number of observed changes in the prioritisation of needs identified in the region between the first and second meetings (Table 4-5). In the second meeting, territorial and chain projects emerged as the top priority, climbing from fourth place. Similarly, resources for investments rose from third to second place, highlighting the importance of securing funding to support these initiatives. Conversely, transformation chains for plant residues, which was the top priority in the first meeting, shifted to third place. Notably, thermoplastic starch for biodegradable materials made a significant leap from twelfth to fourth place, signalling an increasing recognition of sustainable and innovative materials within the region.

On the other hand, some priorities remained consistent, such as dissemination and visibility, which stayed in fifth place, reflecting the ongoing importance of public engagement and communication. Building critical mass with public support and collection costs were not prioritised in the second meeting. Changes in lower-priority items, such as drying plants rising from eleventh to ninth and material storage and sorting areas dropping from eighth to twelfth, suggest a recalibration of logistical and operational considerations. Overall, the revised prioritisation reflects an approach that balances innovation, funding, and regional collaboration to address emerging challenges and opportunities.

Table 4-5. Results on the calibration of needs in the Italian region

Requirements	2° meeting	1°meeting	
Territorial and chain projects	1	4	↑
Resources of investments	2	3	↑
Transformation chains for plant residues	3	1	↓
Thermoplastic starch for biodegradable materials	4	12	↑
Dissemination and visibility (publicity)	5	5	-
Innovation	6	2	↓
Transformation systems	7	6	↓
Mobile forest equipment (e.g. mobile sawmills)	8	9	↑
Drying plants	9	11	↑
Regulatory issues	10	10	-
Building critical mass with public support	11	NO	
Material storage and sorting areas	12	8	↓
Recovery chains for spent substrates	13	7	↓
Collection costs (how can they be covered?)	14	NO	

4.4 Section 3: Economic variables

4.4.1 Supply Value

FAN members discussed the supply value of various biomass products, displayed in Table 4-6 below. The supply values reflect their market potential. Biomass 1 (Biochar) is priced at €0.36/kg, Biomass 2 (Biofertiliser) at €0.55/kg, and Biomass 3 (Compost from organic effluents) at €2.80/kg. These prices represent the perceived value of these products based on production complexity and application benefits.

4.4.2 Subrogation Value

FAN members also provided insights into the subrogation values (Table 4-6), which indicate the replacement costs of bio-based products relative to traditional fertilisers. Organic Biomass Waste is valued at €0.14/kg, Pruning Waste at €0.031/kg, Waste Treatment at €0.03/kg, and Herbaceous Biomass at €1.70/kg. These values suggest that bio-based alternatives are seen as cost-effective and sustainable solutions for agricultural practices.

Table 4-6. Economic variables supply value and subrogation value of biomasses in the Italian region

Supply Value	Subrogation value
Biomass 1- Biochar 0.36 €/kg	Bio-based Product 1- Organic biomass waste: € 0.14 €/kg
Biomass 2- Biofertiliser: 0.55 €/kg	Bio-based Product 2 – Pruning waste: 0.031 €/kg
Biomass 3- Compost from organic effluents: 2.8 €/kg	Bio-based Product 3 – Waste Treatment 0.03 €/kg
	Bio-based Product 4- Herbaceous biomass 1.7 €/kg

5 Spanish FAN

5.1 Workshop details

Table 5-1. Description of BBTs selected for debate among FAN members for their suitability to the Andalusian region of Spain.

Venue	Online
Date	11/11/2024
Format	Microsoft Teams
Attendee number	9
Name of the event	Workshop 2: Validation and Prioritisation of BBTs in Andalusia, Spain

5.2 Section 1: Debate over the BBTs and feasibility for the Spanish region.

The meeting was organised to be held online via Microsoft Teams at a time that suited all FAN members. In the first part of the workshop, the methodology to be followed in the meeting, as well as the list of bio-based technologies pre-selected for this activity, were sent to the attendees by e-mail one week prior to the workshop taking place. On the other hand, a board was prepared in the Miroboard (**Error! Reference source not found.**) application where the instructions, the list of BBTs (see Table 5-1) with the key information of each of them, the link, and the questions for each BBTs with the different scoring options, were included.

Figure 5-1. A snapshot of part (a) of the workshop taking place in Miroboard

Table 5-2. Description of BBTs selected for debate among FAN members for their suitability to the Andalusian region.

No.	BBT Code	BBT Description
1	FI12-ForestChip4Farm/FC4FH	Farm-level heating plants (400-500kW) to use fresh forest-chips
2	DE13-Lignocellulosic Biorefinery/LIGNO	Anaerobic digestion of farm residues (wood, grass, straw)
3	EL14-BIO2CHP/B2CHP	Container-sized power generator that converts solid organic residues into energy on-site.
4	IT20-Clean-ER/CLINR	Small wood chipping machine for collecting wood biomass from mountain forests and their pyrolysis to obtain energy and biochar
5	ES-Biochar/BIOCH	Use of prunings for biochar production
6	EL21-ΕΛΑΙΩΝΑΣ/OLFER	Utilisation of olive residues for the production of compost and biochar
7	ES-OleoValoriza/OLIVE	Recovery of sludge from olive-mill ponds through a composting process.
8	ES-OleoValoriza/OLIV2	The use of olive trees to produce compost
9	EL13-OLIHHERB/OLIVE	Exploitation of olive leaves (rich in polyphenols and other bioactive ingredients) to produce herbal infusions and natural food additives
10	IE23-SBDP/BGAS	Small scale biogas production from on-farm feedstock

5.2.1 Results on the prioritisation of BBTs in the region

The Andalusian FAN evaluated the list of BBTs outlined in Table 5-1 above to assess their suitability for the region, with weightage scores reflecting their alignment with regional needs and challenges. Among the technologies, BBT no. 6 - EL21-ΕΛΑΙΩΝΑΣ/OLFER obtained the highest average score, followed by BBT no. 8 and 9 - ES-OleoValoriza/OLIV2 and EL13-OLIHHERB/OLIVE (both 4.4) emphasising the region's focus on olive-based innovations, aligning with Andalusia's dominant olive industry. Mid-ranked technologies such as ES-Biochar/BIOCH (BBT no. 5) (3.6) and IE23-SBDP/BGAS (BBT no. 10) (3.8) show promise in carbon sequestration and biogas production, supporting sustainability goals. However, lower-ranked options like DE13-Lignocellulosic Biorefinery/LIGNO (BBT no. 2) (2.8) and IT20-Clean-ER/CLINR (BBT no. 4) (3.0) were not as highly ranked by FAN members in terms of feasibility and alignment with local needs. FI12-ForestChip4Farm/FC4FH (BBT no. 1), with a score of 3.2, falls in the mid-to-lower range of the prioritisation. This suggests it holds some potential but may not be as impactful or regionally aligned as the top-ranked technologies (Table 5-3).

Table 5-3. Summary of the prioritisation of each BBT for each key question in the Andalusian region

Questions	Is the BBT suitable for the available resources in the region?	Is the BBT suitable for the region's needs?	Does this BBT have the potential to develop a value chain?	Economic potential of the BBT for the region	Will the BBT benefit the environment and society in the region?	Weighting (average)
BBT 1	+3	+3	+3	+3	+4	3.2
BBT 2	+3	+3	+2	+3	+3	2.8
BBT 3	+4	+4	+3	+4	+4	3.8
BBT 4	+3	+3	+3	+3	+3	3
BBT 5	+4	+4	+3	+3	+4	3.6
BBT 6	+4	+5	+5	+4	+5	4.6
BBT 7	+4	+5	+4	+4	+4	4.2
BBT 8	+5	+5	+4	+4	+4	4.4
BBT 9	+4	+5	+4	+4	+5	4.4
BBT10	+4	+3	+3	+4	+5	3.8

5.3 Section 2: Recalibration of Needs and Resources for the region

5.3.1 Recalibration of resources in the region

The resources and needs identified during the first workshop were re-evaluated in order to update their relative prioritisation. A dynamic discussion was held live and both the updated resources and needs in the region were prioritised. New resources and new needs were identified. Also, some of the resources were renamed to give better comprehension. The results for this section regarding the biomass resources in the region are shown in Table 5-4. The changes in this table reflect recalibrations made by FAN members.

The recalibration of resources between the first and second FAN workshop reveal a shift toward prioritising agricultural residues and by products over forestry-based resources in Andalusia's bioeconomy. In Workshop 2, olive tree pruning residues and olive pits have greater prioritisation, reflecting the region's agricultural dominance and the strategic potential of olive-related by products. Similarly, pruning residues and biomass from fruits and vegetables have replaced forestry-focused materials like pine forest pruning residues and eucalyptus debris. Processing by products such as pomace and almond shells also gain prominence, highlighting their economic potential. In contrast,

broader categories from Workshop 1, such as wood and olive stone, have been refined into more actionable, high-value streams. Slurry remains a consistent priority, though its relative importance decreased as other resources increased in priority.

Overall, the changes reflect a more targeted approach, prioritising abundant, and high-impact resources like olive and almond residues over less specific or forestry-based alternatives. These shifts align Andalusia's bioeconomy strategy with its regional prevalent industries (Table 5-4).

Table 5-4. Results on the calibration of resources available in the Italian RR

Resources (Update - workshop 2)	Resources (identified in workshop 1)
1. Olive tree pruning residues	Pine forest pruning residues
2. Pruning residues from agricultural plantations	Eucalyptus forest pruning debris
3. Biomass from fruit and vegetables	Slurry
4. Pomace	Wood
5. Residues from silvicultural treatments	Olive stone
6. Slurry	Olive pruning residues
7. Olive pits	Fruits and vegetables biomass
8. Almond shells	

Figure 5-2. A snapshot of Part 2 of the workshop - Results and prioritisation of biomass resources taken from Mentimeter

5.3.2 Recalibration of needs in the region

The recalibration of needs for adoption of circular process in Andalusia discussed in Workshop 2 highlight a number of key shifts (Table 5-5). Compared to Workshop 1, there is a stronger focus on the lack of technical and financial support policies (1), reflecting a need for better infrastructure and market readiness. This replaces the earlier emphasis on the absence of biorefineries or biomass management plants close to production sites (2).

The issue of low cost-efficiency of technology (2) also takes precedence in Workshop 2, highlighting the need for market-ready, cost-effective solutions, whereas Workshop 1 focused more on logistical issues like high moisture content (3). The recalibration further stresses challenges like biomass storage in the forestry sector (10) and seasonal biomass generation (5), which remain critical.

Additionally, Workshop 2 places greater emphasis on the lack of awareness about circular bioeconomy (4) and the low added value of products (6), along with the need for regulatory standards for bio-products (7). These recalibrations underscore the importance of market stability, infrastructure, and awareness to scale circular processes effectively.

Table 5-5. Results on the calibration of needs in the Andalusian region

Needs (Update - workshop 2)	Needs (identified in workshop 1)
1. Lack of technical and financial support policies for the generation of bio products	1. Absence of biorefineries or biomass management plants close to the production site for local biomass processing
2. Low cost-efficiency ratio of the technology, not available in the market	2. High costs of storage and transport of products with a high percentage of moisture
3. Lack of biorefineries or biomass management plants close to the production site	3. Bio-products currently do not have enough added value to make the logistics cost profitable.
4. Lack of awareness about the concept of circular bioeconomy in the agricultural and forestry sectors	4. Available technologies with a bad efficiency cost ratio, mainly still at pilot phase, not available in the market. Large number of R&D projects but not all are scalable.
5. Logistical issues due to the seasonal generation of biomass	5. Weeding, storage, cluching of forest increase the biomass cost.
6. Low added value of products to make the logistical cost of products profitable	6. Logistics problems due to seasonal biomass generation. No guarantee of a stable prize of the bio-product in the market (uncertainty that makes biomass valorisation not profitable) Lack of awareness about circular bioeconomy concept to the agricultural and forest producer (biomass supplier) and the society as a whole.
7. Lack of regulation and standards concerning substitute bio-products generated with biotechnologies	
8. Absence of a stable price for the bio-product in the market (uncertainty)	
9. High storage and transportation costs of products with a high percentage of humidity	
10. Residues and storage issues in the forestry sector, increasing the cost of biomass	

Figure 5-3. Results on the prioritisation of needs in the Andalusian region from Mentimeter

5.4 Section 3: Economic variables

A number of issues were identified with respect to the economic and subrogation values of the biomasses in section 2 of the workshop as these were aspects that participants were not familiar with. Economic value to biomasses/by-products were difficult aspects to give answers to. It was discussed how most biomasses produced on farms and forestry holdings do not give specific values since it is incorporated into the soil on agricultural land, or a removal service is contracted at no cost to the farm. By-products in the fields are seen as a “cost” not as a “value”. As during workshop 1, this economic valorisation was difficult to approach. To get an estimate of their economic valuation, it was decided to give values on a comparable basis. In this way, a ranking was obtained with the vision of the attendees in relation to which of the biomasses identified in the agroforestry sector they see as products of greater or lesser value.

In the same way, the products were analysed. A distinction was made between energy generation products (biogas and biofuels) and other bio-products such as bio-fertilisers, compost and other biomaterials.

The results on the economic valuation of the biomasses (supply chain) and products obtained (subrogated value) are displayed in below (table 5-6):

5.4.1 Supply value

In terms of supply value, olive pits were noted as the most valuable resource at 135 €/ton, followed by pomace (35.2 €/ton) and silvicultural residues (34.4 €/ton), which are suited for biofuel and compost production. Other resources like olive tree pruning residues (26.8 €/ton) and pruning residues from agricultural plantations (18.6 €/ton) have moderate value, while almond shells (10.8 €/ton) and slurry (17.8 €/ton) are less expensive but still hold potential for bioenergy or bioproducts.

5.4.2 Subrogation value

Regarding subrogation value, biomass from fruits and vegetables (190.4 €/ton) offers the highest potential for replacing traditional fertilisers, particularly as bio-fertilisers. Pomace and olive tree pruning residues can also serve as alternatives in composting and biofuels, though they are less efficient as fertiliser substitutes. Slurry has moderate subrogation value due to its ability to produce organic acids and bio-composites, while olive pits and almond shells are more specialised for high-value applications in the food, cosmetic, and pharmaceutical industries rather than direct fertiliser replacement.

Table 5-6. Economic variables supply value and subrogation value of biomasses in the Andalusian region

Supply Value	Subrogation value
Olive tree pruning residues: 26,8 €/ton	Biofuel: 6 €/kWh
Pruning residues from agricultural plantations: 18,6 €/ton	Biogas: 33 €/kWh
Biomass from fruit and vegetables: 13,6 €/ton	Biofertilisers: 190,4 €/ton
Pomace: 35,2 €/ton	Compost: 55 €/ton
Residues from silvicultural treatments: 34,4 €/ton	Ashes from agricultural residues: 21,8 €/ton
Slurry: 17,8 €/ton	Chemicals: organic acids, bioplastics, biocomposites: 110,6 €/ton
Olive pits: 135 €/ton	Bioactive compounds for the food, cosmetics and pharmaceutical industries: 200,2 €/ton
Almond shells: 10,8 €/ton	

¿Cuál cree que es el valor de cada biomasa?

Bioenergía

¿Cuál cree que es el precio del producto sustitutivo obtenido?

Figure 5-4. Results on the economic evaluation of biomasses from Mentimeter in the Andalusian region from Mentimeter

6 Greek FAN

6.1 Workshop details

Table 6-1. Details of workshop 3 in the Greek FAN

Venue	online
Date	30/10/2024
Format	Online via Microsoft Teams and Mentimeter
Attendee number	14
Name of the event	Workshop 2: Validation and Prioritisation of BBTs in Greece

6.2 Section 1: Debate over the BBTs and feasibility for their region.

During the first phase of the workshop, a list of 13 BBTs were introduced by the AFS team to the FAN members, these BBTs were taken from EU Operational Groups, and presented to FAN members for debate in order to discuss their feasibility for their RR. These are displayed in Table 6-2 below:

The entirety of the methodology proposed in deliverable D1.4, Methodology on the Validation and Prioritisation of BBTs per Region [Greece], was followed. For recording the responses, the Mentimeter application (<https://www.mentimeter.com/>) was used.

Table 6-2. Description of BBTs selected for debate among FAN members for their suitability to the Greek region.

No.	BBT code	BBT Description
1	OLEOVALORIZA	(1) Recovery of sludge from olive-mill ponds through a composting process (2) Use of olive trees residues to produce compost
2	ΕΛΑΙΩΝΑΣ/OLFER	Utilisation of olive residues for the production of compost and biochar
3	AGROSCHOOLBUS.BIO	Recovery of the nutrients contained in the residues (branches, leaves) of olive trees (and other productive trees) through composting
4	COMPOST-INNO/COMPO	Improvement of compost production from the processing of by-product-waste mixtures from various sources
5	WOOD2BIOGAS/WD2BG	Gasification of wood and the use of wood syngas plus biogas from manure to produce biomethane
6	LIGNOCELLULOSIC BIOREFINERY/LIGNO	Anaerobic digestion of farm residues (wood, grass, straw)
7	GO-GRASS/GOGRS	This technology converts low nutritional quality grass from the wetlands into biochar for soil improvement
8	BIOACTAM/BIOAA	Discontinuous biochar production
9	MIXBIOPELLS/PLTIZ	Pelletizing mixed biomass residues and waste from agriculture and forestry
10	OLIHERB	Exploitation of olive leaves (rich in polyphenols and other bioactive ingredients) to produce herbal infusions and natural food additives
11	REFERTIL/3RZRO	3R zero emission pyrolysis plant recycles and reuses un-exploited biomass for recovery of concentrated Phosphorus and natural BioPhosphate products.
12	GRASSBIOWERT/BWERT	Grass biorefinery to produce bio-based materials and energy
13	COBRA/COBRA	Oilseed crops' residues are biorefined to produce bioactive compounds

As common for the workshops held in each RR, each BBT was prioritised with a score from -5 to +5 according to the methodology from the guidelines in section 3.1 of this document; Guidelines to Debate over the BBTs and feasibility for their region developed by MTU and Teagasc.

6.2.1 Results on the prioritisation of BBTs in the region

The weightage scores reflecting the alignment of each of the 13 BBTs from table 6-2 are with regional needs and challenges are displayed in Table 6-3.

A number of BBTs aligned strongly with the needs and challenges of the region. For example, BBT1 (OLEOVALORIZA) received a high score (4.6). This technology focuses on recovering sludge from olive-mill ponds and using olive tree residues to produce compost. Its strong alignment highlights the significance of addressing olive mill by-products, which are a major concern in Mediterranean regions like Greece. Similarly, BBT2 (ΕΛΑΙΩΝΑΣ/OLFER) obtained a high score of 4.4, this focuses on using olive residues for compost and biochar. It complements BBT1 by providing an alternative use for similar by-products. BBT3 (AGROSCHOOLBUS.BIO) obtained a score of 4.2, emphasising nutrient recovery from olive and other tree residues through composting. This indicates a strong need for sustainable waste management in olive-centric agricultural systems. While BBT4 (COMPOST-INNO/COMPO) received a weight of 3.6, which aims to improve compost production using diverse waste sources.

BBT 6 (LIGNOCELLULOSIC BIOREFINERY/LIGNO) scored 3.2 reflecting moderate alignment with the resources and needs of the region.

Lower scoring BBTs that demonstrated limited alignment included MIXBIOPELLS/PLTIZ (BBT9): which scored 1.8, OLIHERB (BBT10): which scored 1.2, BIOACTAM/BIOAA (BBT8): which scored 0.8, and REFERTIL/3RZRO (BBT11): which scored 0.4.

GO-GRASS/GOGRS (BBT7), GRASSBIOWERT/BWERT (BBT12), and COBRA/COBRA (BBT13): All scored 0.2, indicating minimal alignment with the region's needs. These technologies target grasses and oilseed crops, demonstrating less alignment in the region compared to olive-focused applications.

WOOD2BIOGAS/WD2BG (BBT5): Surprisingly scored 0, showing no alignment with local needs, possibly due to a lack of wood resources or interest in biomethane production.

There was an overall focus on biomasses related to olive production: The top-scoring technologies (BBT1, BBT2, BBT3) heavily focus on olive-related residues. This reflects the regional importance of olive farming and the need for sustainable by-product management.

Composting vs. Energy: Composting technologies rank higher than biochar or energy-focused methods, indicating a preference for soil improvement over energy recovery.

Specialised Applications: Niche applications like herbal infusions (BBT10) and bio refined compounds (BBT13) received lower scores.

Grass and wood-based technologies (BBT5, BBT7, BBT12) scored poorly, reflecting a lack of alignment with local resources and needs in light of the primary agricultural and forestry production in the area.

Table 6-3. Summary of the prioritisation of each BBT for each key question

Questions	Is the BBT suitable for the available resources in the region?	Is the BBT suitable for the region's needs?	Does this BBT have the potential to develop a value chain?	Economic potential of the BBT for the region	Will the BBT benefit the environment and society in the region?	Weighting (average)
BBT 1	+5	+4	+5	+4	+5	4.6
BBT 2	+5	+4	+5	+4	+4	4.4
BBT 3	+5	+4	+4	+4	+4	4.2
BBT 4	+4	+3	+4	+3	+4	3.6
BBT 5	+2	0	-2	+1	-1	0
BBT 6	+5	+4	+3	+4	0	3.2
BBT 7	+2	0	-3	0	+2	0.2
BBT 8	+2	0	0	+1	+1	0.8
BBT 9	+1	+1	+2	+2	+3	1.8
BBT10	+2	0	+2	0	+2	1.2
BBT11	+1	0	-1	1	1	0.4
BBT12	+2	0	-3	0	+2	0.2
BBT13	+2	0	-3	0	+2	0.2

6.3 Section 2: Recalibration of Needs and Resources for the region

6.3.1 Recalibration of resources in the region

In the initial workshop 'Identification and prioritisation of resources and needs per region' conducted earlier in 2024, the resources identified as the most significant in terms of their relative abundance in the region were the following:

- (1) Olive and olive oil production biomass and prunings
- (2) Prunings and grass from fruit trees
- (3) Stone-fruit residue
- (4) Greenhouse vegetable plant biomass
- (5) Sheep wool
- (6) Chestnut skin

Although biomass derived from olive trees is closely related to the biomass from olive mills, their nature as resources is quite different. Consequently, the resource "olive and olive oil production biomass and prunings" mentioned in the first workshop was deemed necessary to split into olive mill waste and olive tree biomass and prunings. Then, the similarity between olive tree biomass and that derived from other fruit-bearing trees, were unified and presented as a resource called "tree residues", encompassing biomass from all types of trees.

Furthermore, in light of the fact that greenhouse vegetable plant biomass does not differ in nature from other plant-based biomass except for its place of origin, it was replaced by the term 'biomass from various resources'.

In addition, during the period between the two workshops, it was found that manure is the dominant biomass produced in livestock farming and widely used at most plant producing units. As such, it was essential to include it among the resources under evaluation, which was confirmed by its subsequent positive assessment.

Straw and avocado were "feedstock" for bio-based technologies that were weighted in Section 1; therefore, it was deemed appropriate to evaluate them as well. Straw is a widely available biomass in the region, while avocado is an emerging alternative cultivar in Greece, and was deemed to be similar in nature to the referral to oilseed in the first workshop.

Meanwhile, chestnut skin and sheep wool were referenced by FAN members in the first workshop but not the second. Additionally, no references to these resources emerged during the interval between the two workshops.

Based on all the above, the list of resources evaluated was modified as follows:

- (1) Olive mill waste
- (2) Tree residues
- (3) Grass
- (4) Oilseeds
- (5) Biomass from various resources

- (6) Avocado
- (7) Straw
- (8) Manure

The recalibrated rankings highlight a consistent focus on olive-related resources, with **olive mill waste** maintaining its top priority and **tree residues** slightly downgraded (from 2nd to 3rd). **Manure** emerged as a new, high-priority addition (2nd), reflecting growing interest in its bioeconomy potential. **Grass** saw a notable drop (from 3rd to 5th), indicating reduced relevance, while **biomass from various sources** was slightly upgraded (from 6th to 5th), showing an interest in diversifying resource use. New additions like **straw** (7th) and **avocado** (8th) suggest expanding attention to other emerging resources, albeit with lower immediate importance. These changes reflect a balance between addressing dominant regional waste streams and exploring broader bioeconomy opportunities.

Table 6-4. Results on the calibration of resources available in the Greek RR

	final ranking	initial ranking	difference
olive mill waste	1	1	↔
manure	2		
tree residues	3	2	↓1
oilseeds	4	4	↔
grass	5	3	↓2
biomass from various sources	6	5	↑1
straw	7		
avocado	8		

6.3.2 Recalibration of needs in the region

The recalibration of needs for adoption of circular process in Greece discussed in Workshop 2 highlight a number of key shifts (Table 5-5). The top need is now a system for technology availability and know-how for farmers, upgraded from 2nd to 1st, reflecting the importance of empowering farmers with tools and knowledge. Demonstration and piloting schemes (upgraded from 3rd to 2nd) and education on biomass treatment protocols (upgraded from 4th to 3rd) emphasise a growing focus on practical and educational initiatives to enhance bioeconomy practices. Inter-sectoral collaboration dropped from 1st to 4th, with more attention being paid to needs at primary production level. Meanwhile, wool processing technology remains unchanged in 5th place, indicating steady but limited relevance. These adjustments reflect a stronger emphasis on education, farmer support, and practical demonstrations.

Table 6-5. Results on the calibration of needs in the Greek region

Identified needs for the Greek region	final ranking	initial ranking	difference
A system for the availability of processing technology and the provision of the necessary know-how to farmers	1	2	↑1
Demonstration/Experimental/Piloting schemes for educational purposes	2	3	↑1
Education on specific treatment protocols for the quality of the bio-mass streams	3	4	↑1
Inter-sectoral collaboration to avoid residue bio-mass contamination	4	1	↓3
Wool processing technology for use in agriculture	5	5	↔

6.4 Section 3: Economic variables

Members of the Greek FAN also provided insights into the subrogation values (Table 6-6), which indicate the replacement costs of bio-based products relative to traditional fertilisers.

6.4.1 Supply value

Table 6-6 highlights the value placed on the various biomasses in Greece. Olive mill waste (€0.05–0.10/kg) and manure (€0.02–0.05/kg) are cost-effective by-products, suitable for reuse in energy and agriculture. Tree residues (€0.01–0.03/kg) were deemed to have the lowest value, reflecting their abundance in forestry. Grass (€0.02–0.05/kg) was also relatively inexpensive. In contrast, oilseeds (€0.30–0.50/kg) are more valuable due to their high value in feed and biofuel applications.

6.4.2 Subrogation value

The subrogation values in the table 6-6 illustrate the economic benefits derived from the utilisation of the biomasses in various applications:

Bioenergy was valued at €1.10 per litre, demonstrating potential to substitute traditional fossil fuels. A value of 0.50 €/kg for Soil Amelioration emphasises the importance of organic amendments in improving soil fertility and structure, contributing to sustainable agricultural practices. Biochar (1.50 €/kg) obtained the highest subrogation value at €1.50 per kilogram highlighting its role in carbon sequestration, enhancing soil quality, and its increasing relevance in climate mitigation strategies. Animal Feed (0.15–0.40 €/kg): the range of which depends on the nutritional profile and quality of the feed, reflecting its utility in supporting livestock productivity and reducing reliance on traditional feedstocks. Biomass converted into pellets for energy purposes commands a significant subrogation

value of €400 per ton. This high value demonstrates the demand for pellets in heating and power generation, highlighting their efficiency and role in renewable energy systems.

Table 6-6. Economic variables supply value and subrogation value of biomasses in the Greek region

supply value		subrogation value		
olive mill waste	0.05-0.10 €/kg	bioenergy	1.10	€/lt
manure	0.02-0.05 €/kg	soil amelioration	0.50	€/kg
tree residues	0.01-0.03 €/kg	biochar	1.50	€/kg
oilseeds	0.30-0.50 €/kg	animal feed	0-15-0.40	€/kg
grass	0.02-0.05 €/kg	pellets	400	€/ton

Overall, this FAN meeting provided a comprehensive "platform" for reevaluating the prioritisation of bio-based technologies, highlighting their applicability and potential within the Greek context. Using the structured methodology outlined in deliverable D1.4, the meeting facilitated detailed discussions on the suitability, economic potential, and environmental benefits of various technologies. Additionally, the identification of specific needs and resources reaffirmed the region's unique opportunities for adopting bio-based solutions. The insights and data collected during this session lay a solid foundation for advancing sustainable development and fostering innovation in bio-based technologies.

7 Czech FAN

7.1 Workshop details

Table 7-1. Details of workshop 3 in the Czech FAN

Workshop Details	
Venue	Brno, Czech Republic
Date	28/11/2024
Format	In-person
Attendee number	97
Name of the event	Current knowledge of biomass resources and processing needs in Czech Republic

7.2 Section 1: Debate over the BBTs and feasibility for their region.

During the first phase of the in-person workshop, a list of 10 BBTs were introduced by the BIO EAST HUB team to the FAN members, these BBTs were taken from EU Operational Groups, and presented to FAN members for debate in order to discuss their feasibility for their RR. These are displayed in Table 6-2:

Table 7-2. Description of BBTs selected for debate among FAN members for their suitability to the Czech region.

No.	BBT code	BBT Description
1	FI12-ForestChip4Farm/FC4FH	farm-level heating plants (400-500kW) to use fresh forest-chips
2	HU16-REFERTIL/3RZRO	3R zero emission pyrolysis plant recycles and reuses un-exploited biomass for recovery of concentrated Phosphorus and natural BioPhosphate products.
3	EE18-Hay Biosyngas/HAYBG	Hay and agroforestry residues are processed using heat and biocatalytic pyrolysis to produce biochar
4	DE31-MixBioPells/PLTIZ	Pelletizing mixed biomass residues and waste from agriculture and forestry
5	DE33-BIOlution/BIOLT	dry moulding production technology to create sustainable packaging solutions
6	IT37-BIOECO_FLIES/W2BSF	Agricultural residues will be used to grow Black Soldier Fly larvae, which will be processed into protein, lipid, and chitin fractions
7	CZ70-TJ-Grow_media/GROW	Use liquid part of digestate – fugate originated from the biogas plant.
8	CZ76-TH-Compost_biochar/COMP	Composting process (intensification of organic matter decomposition) by addition of biochar.
9	FR21-SeCoPPA /ALFLF	Alfalfa is dried and granulated using a dryer powered by solar energy, wood residues and electricity
10	ES-LIFE Smart Fertirrigation/FRTGN	Integrated pig manure digestate processing for direct injection of organic liquid fertilizer into irrigation systems

7.2.1 Results on the prioritisation of BBTs in the region

The weightage scores reflecting the alignment of each of the 10 BBTs from table 7-2 are with regional needs and challenges are displayed in Table 7-3.

Technology CZ76-TH-Compost_biochar obtained the highest score (4.2), demonstrating its alignment with the resources and challenges of the region by enhancing composting with biochar, a solution well-suited to the Czech Republic's agricultural sector and organic waste streams. Similarly, CZ70-TJ-Grow_media (3.8), which repurposes biogas plant digestate, aligns closely with the Czech region's

established biogas infrastructure, effectively integrating waste recycling with sustainable nutrient management.

Moderately scored technologies also show reasonable alignment. DE31-MixBioPells (score of 3.6) capitalises on mixed biomass residues from agriculture and forestry, aligning with the biomass resources available in the region. HU16-REFERTIL (score of 3.2) addresses circular nutrient management by recovering phosphorus and biophosphate products from unexploited biomass, which aligns with agricultural sustainability goals. FR21-SeCoPPA (3.2), which processes alfalfa using renewable energy sources, fits well in regions aiming to combine renewable energy and sustainable feed solutions.

In contrast, lower-scoring technologies reflect weaker alignment with regional resources or priorities. For instance, IT37-BIOECO_FLIES (score of 1.4), which uses agricultural residues to produce Black Soldier Fly larvae for protein and lipid extraction, demonstrated limited potential, while FI12-ForestChip4Farm (score of 2.6), utilising fresh forest chips for farm-level heating, and ES-LIFE Smart Fertirrigation (score of 2.4), which injects processed pig manure digestate into irrigation systems, may only partially address the Czech region's resource availability or specific agricultural needs.

Table 7-3. Summary of the prioritisation of each BBT for each key question

Questions	Is the BBT suitable for the available resources in the region?	Is the BBT suitable for the region's needs?	Does this BBT have the potential to develop a value chain?	Economic potential of the BBT for the region	Will the BBT benefit the environment and society in the region?	Weighting (average)
BBT 1	+4	+3	+2	+2	+2	2.6
BBT 2	+3	+3	+3	+3	+4	3.2
BBT 3	+3	+2	+3	+3	+4	3
BBT 4	+4	+3	+4	+4	+3	3.6
BBT 5	+2	+2	+3	+2	+2	2.2
BBT 6	+2	0	+2	+2	+1	1.4
BBT 7	+4	+4	+3	+4	+4	3.8
BBT 8	+5	+4	+4	+4	+4	4.2
BBT 9	+4	+4	+3	+3	+2	3.2
BBT10	+2	+3	+2	+2	+3	2.4

7.3 Section 2: Recalibration of Needs and Resources for the region

7.3.1 Recalibration of resources in the region

Table 7-4 presents a list of biomass resources identified in the Czech region, initially outlined in a meeting held in April 2024 and later revisited in November 2024 and recalibrated during a follow-up meeting. Interestingly, the rankings and inclusion of resources remained consistent across both meetings, reflecting an overall agreement on the relative importance and availability of these resources.

Table 7-4. Results on the calibration of resources available in the Czech RR

Resources meeting 2	Resources meeting 3
Plant and forest wastes	Plant and forest wastes
Organic wastes from industrial production	Organic wastes from industrial production
Wastes from livestock production	Wastes from livestock production
Municipal organic waste	Municipal organic waste
Fast-growing woody plants	Fast-growing woody plants
Grape seeds	Grape seeds
Residues {stillage (from distillery)}	Residues {stillage (from distillery)}
	Pits
	Sewage sludge
	Used cooking oil

7.3.2 Recalibration of needs in the region

Table 7-5 presents a list of biomass needs identified in the Czech region, initially outlined in a meeting held in April 2024 and later revisited in November 2024 and recalibrated during a follow-up meeting. In similar fashion to the resources outline in table 7-4, FAN members believed that the rankings and inclusion of needs remained consistent across both meetings, reflecting an overall agreement on the relative importance and availability of these resources.

Table 7-5. Results on the calibration of needs in the Czech region

Needs meeting 2	Needs meeting 3
Building a network of buyers for compost from composting plants, as compost is almost unmarketable or very little used in the Highlands. Farmers in the region have enough manure due to livestock production and do not need compost. However, it is suitable, among others, for areas in drinking water protection zones or protected landscape areas, of which there are many in the region.	Building a network of buyers for compost from composting plants, as compost is almost unmarketable or very little used in the Highlands. Farmers in the region have enough manure due to livestock production and do not need compost. However, it is suitable, among others, for areas in drinking water protection zones or protected landscape areas, of which there are many in the region.
Use of food waste and kitchen waste for biogas and compost production	Use of food waste and kitchen waste for biogas and compost production
A long-term survey carried out by ZERA identified problems related to insufficient technological interconnection between composting plants, biogas plants and wastewater treatment plants	A long-term survey carried out by ZERA identified problems related to insufficient technological interconnection between composting plants, biogas plants and wastewater treatment plants
Availability of biomass combustion boilers	Availability of biomass combustion boilers
Motivation of cider, distilleries and wineries to recover waste biomass in biogas plants, by incineration or composting	Motivation of cider, distilleries and wineries to recover waste biomass in biogas plants, by incineration or composting
Use of gastro and kitchen waste for biogas and compost production	Use of gastro and kitchen waste for biogas and compost production
Promote wastewater treatment combined with algae cultivation for biomass	Promote wastewater treatment combined with algae cultivation for biomass

7.4 Section 3: Economic variables

7.4.1 Supply value

The estimated Supply Values for the various bio-based inputs are displayed in table 7-6, demonstrating the costs that BBT owners might incur to procure these materials. The prices vary significantly, reflecting the availability, processing requirements, and logistical considerations for each type of input.

Plant and forest wastes are among the most less valuable resources at €13.5/t, as a result of their abundance and ease of collection. Similarly, organic wastes from industrial production, priced at €2/m³, are relatively economical. Wastes from livestock production, costing €15/t, are slightly more expensive due to the additional effort required for transportation and handling.

On the higher end, municipal organic waste is valued at €51/t, reflecting the expenses associated with collection, sorting, and preliminary treatment by municipal systems. Fast-growing woody plants have the highest price in the table at €59/t, which can be attributed to the costs of cultivation, harvesting, and transportation.

Grape seeds and pits are priced at €0.78/kg and €6/kg, respectively. Their higher unit prices reflect their niche applications and potential for generating high-value bio-based products. Residues from distilleries (stillage), at €47/t, offer a moderately priced resource for valorisation, benefiting from consistent supply chains in the alcohol industry. Sewage sludge, at €17.89/t, represents a mid-range option with its value influenced by processing requirements for safe utilisation. Finally, used cooking oil is priced at €0.24/l, making it an economical liquid bio-input often used in biofuel production.

Table 7-6. Economic supply value of biomasses in the Czech region

ID	Primary or secondary resources	Supply Value per Kg/litre/tonne
1	Plant and forest wastes	13,5 €/t
2	Organic wastes from industrial production	2 €/m ³
3	Wastes from livestock production	15 €/t
4	Municipal organic waste	51 €/t
5	Fast-growing woody plants	59 €/t
6	Grape seeds	0,78 €/kg
7	Residues {stillage (from distillery)}	47 €/t
8	Pits	6 €/kg
9	Sewage sludge	17,89 €/t
10	Used cooking oil	0,24 €/l

7.4.2 Subrogation value

The subrogation values of the various BBTs are displayed below in table 7-7, reflecting the cost of these innovative products compared to conventional alternatives. The ForestChip4Farm project (FI12) produces heating fuel from fresh forest chips, priced at 19 €/m³, relatively economical for renewable energy solutions at the farm level. In contrast, REFERTIL (HU16) offers phosphorus fertilisers derived from biochar and compost at 1.7 €/kg, highlighting a cost-effective alternative to conventional chemical fertilisers. Similarly, Hay Biosyngas (EE18) provides torrefied hay pellets at 3.20 €/kg, emphasising the value of transforming low-quality biomass into high-energy biochar.

The MixBioPells project (DE31) produces biomass pellets at 126 €/t, a competitive price for energy production when using materials like low-quality wood or straw. On the other hand, BIOlution (DE33) focuses on biodegradable packaging materials, priced at 10.65 €/m², reflecting the added value of sustainable packaging solutions made from agricultural residues such as tomato and wheat waste.

High-value bio-based compounds, such as those produced by BIOECO_FLIES (IT37), are priced at 98 €/m³. This premium reflects the advanced processing of vegetable wastes to produce proteins, fats, and chitin via Black Soldier Fly larvae. Grow_media (CZ) offers an organic growing medium made from liquid digestate at 25 €/m³, making it a cost-effective choice for sustainable agriculture. The

Compost_biochar project (CZ) combines biochar and compost, priced at 120 €/m³, delivering a premium solution for soil health enhancement.

The SeCoPPA project (FR21) provides alfalfa drying using renewable energy sources, priced at 177 €/t, reflecting the high costs of energy-efficient forage drying processes. Lastly, LIFE Smart Fertirrigation (ES) valorises pig manure digestate to produce organic liquid fertiliser at a highly competitive price of 7.1 €/t, offering an economical and sustainable fertiliser alternative.

Table 7-7. Economic subrogation value of biomasses in the Czech region

BBT ID	Project name	Replacement product produced by the BBT	Subrogation Value per Kg/litre/tonne
FI12	ForestChip4Farm	Pilot farm-level heating plant (400-500KW) (fuel: fresh forest chips)	Bio -based product 1: 19 €/m ³
HU16	REFERTIL	Phosphorus fertilisers (biochar and compost products) made from organic waste and food industrial by-product streams	Bio -based product 2: 1,7 €/kg
EE18	Hay Biosyngas	Torrefied hay pellets (biochar)	Bio -based product 3: 3,20 €/kg
DE31	MixBioPells	Biomass pellets for energy production using low quality wood, straw or olive press cake	Bio -based product 4: 126 €/t
DE33	BIOlution	biodegradable packaging materials (produced from small farmer waste like tomato and weat, which are pressed, dried, and converted into fibers for subsequent moulding and laminating)	Bio -based product 5: 10,65 €/m ²
IT37	BIOECO FLIES	High nutritional value compounds (protein, fats, chitin) produced by valorising seasonal vegetable wastes as substarte for Black Soldier Fly Larvae	Bio -based product 6: 98 €/m ³
CZ	Grow media	Organic substrate to be used as growing medium (valorising liquid digestate in its production)	Bio -based product 7: 25 €/m ³
CZ	Compost_biochar	Improved biochar infused compost	Bio -based product 8: 120 €/m ³
FR21	SeCoPPA	Forage (alfalfa) dryer powered by solar energy, wood residues and electricity	Bio -based product 9: 177 €/t
ES	LIFE Smart Fertirrigation	Pig manure digestate valorised in producing organic liquid fertilizer	Bio -based product 10: 7,1 €/t

8 Irish FAN

8.1 Workshop details

Table 8-1. Details of workshop 3 in the Irish FAN

Venue	Online
Date	22/10/2024
Format	Online via MS Teams using Mentimeter and Miroboard
Attendee number	10
Name of the event	Workshop 3: Validation and Prioritisation of BBTs in Ireland

8.2 Section 1: Debate over the BBTs and feasibility for their region.

The meeting was organised to be held online via Microsoft Teams at a time that suited all FAN members. During the first phase of the workshop, 10 BBTs were introduced to the FAN members by the Teagasc team. These BBTs were taken from EU Operational Groups for debate among Irish FAN members to discuss their feasibility for the Irish RR. These are displayed in Table 8-2 below. Similar to the FANs in other regions, the list of 10 BBTs were sent to FAN members 1 week prior to the workshop in order for the members to become familiar with them.

Each BBT was prioritised with a score from -5 to +5, based on the following 5 criteria: (i) Adaptability of the BBT to the region's resources. (ii) Adaptability of the BBT to the region's needs. (iii) Potential of the BBT to develop a value chain in the region. (iv) Economic potential of the BBT for the region. (v) Effects of the BBT on the environment and society in the region.

Table 8-2. Description of BBTs selected for debate among DAN members for their suitability to Ireland.

No.	BBT code	BBT Description
1	IT54-ProBEST	Felling by-products chipped and sold to thermoelectric plants
2	IT55-ProBEST	In the production of forest wood fuels, the incombustible elements (ash) must be limited
3	IT45-Stabilized Litter	Stabilized litter for dairy cows: optimization of the use of litter derived from the solid fraction separated from manure
4	LT33-cogeneration residue	Using biogas production residues as fertilizer
5	DE-Manure Efficiency	Manure is treated before addition to biogas plant so that as much nitrogen, phosphate and water as possible are removed.
6	IT39-Res4Carbon	waste wood chips, biochar and ashes are used to produce an innovative fertiliser
7	LV49-WoodResidueLV	valorisation of forest wood processing by-products into housing insulation, heating materials and fertilizer
8	PL93-GRIST	Organic grain production and processing of brewery residues into meal, using an innovative dehydration
9	DE13-Lignocellulosic Biorefinery	Anaerobic digestion of farm residues (wood, grass, straw)
10	IE23-SBDP	Small scale biogas production from on-farm feedstock

8.2.1 Results on the prioritisation of BBTs in the region

The Irish FAN evaluated the list of BBTs outlined in Table 4-2 above to assess their suitability for the region, with weightage scores reflecting their alignment with regional needs and challenges. Among the technologies, alignment with regional needs and resources was varied. BBT 3 (stabilized litter for dairy cows) obtained the highest weightage, with an average weightage of 3.8, excelling in environmental and social benefits, resource suitability, and economic potential. BBT 9 (anaerobic digestion of farm residues) follows with a weightage of 3.4, demonstrating robust alignment with regional resources and needs. Conversely, BBT 2 (ash management in forest wood fuels) obtained the lowest weightage of (1.0), reflecting limited compatibility with the Irish bioeconomy across all criteria. BBT10 (Small scale biogas production from on-farm feedstock) obtained a comparatively low weightage of 1.9, demonstrating that in the view of FAN members, such technology is not greatly feasible in the Irish RR. Technologies like BBT 4 (biogas production residues as fertilizer) and BBT 5 (treated manure for AD) showed intermediate potential, with average scores of 3.3 and 3.2, respectively.

Table 8-3. Summary of the prioritisation of each BBT for each key question

Questions	Is the BBT suitable for the available resources in the region?	Is the BBT suitable for the region's needs?	Does this BBT have the potential to develop a value chain?	Economic potential of the BBT for the region	Will the BBT benefit the environment and society in the region?	Weighting (average)
BBT 1	3.8	3.4	2.9	2.1	2.9	3.0
BBT 2	1.9	1.1	0.6	0.4	0.9	1.0
BBT 3	3.9	3.9	3.7	3.0	4.4	3.8
BBT 4	3.3	3.0	3.5	3.0	3.9	3.3
BBT 5	4.0	3.4	2.5	2.5	3.6	3.2
BBT 6	2.6	2.2	2.3	1.9	2.3	2.3
BBT 7	2.0	2.6	2.4	1.6	3.2	2.4
BBT 8	2.0	2.1	3.3	2.6	3.1	2.6
BBT 9	3.9	3.7	3.3	2.3	3.7	3.4
BBT10	2.0	2.3	1.5	0.6	2.9	1.9

8.3 Section 2: Recalibration of Needs and Resources for the region

8.3.1 Recalibration of resources in the region

Table 4-4 presents a list of biomass resources identified in the Italian region, initially outlined in a meeting held on 23/04/2024 and later revisited and recalibrated during a follow-up meeting on 22/10/2024. Some key changes in prioritisation of these resources included Pig & Poultry Manure which moved up the list, reflecting its recognition as a valuable nutrient source to meet soil fertility and crop production. Similarly Green Manures & Cover Crops also increased in the list of prioritisations suggesting recognition of their role in sustainable farming and carbon sequestration. Rushes & Gorse remained low in the prioritisation list while there was a reduced focus on Timber Felling Waste, which lowered in priority. By products of meat processing also reduced in prioritisation, as it was not seen as a significant contributory source to circular processes in the wider agricultural sector. Through the FAN discussions on the topic, grass was introduced as an important resource in the region, highlighting its abundance and potential for bioenergy or bio-based product applications. While food waste in general was mentioned in the previous workshop held in April 2024, this was narrowed down to

specifically vegetable waste, or sub-grade vegetable waste by-products that do not meet the standards for supermarkets.

Overall, it was noted that cattle slurry remained the top priority in the region across both meetings, reflecting its abundance due to the prevalence of dairy and meat production systems in the region, as well as its suitability for AD and nutrient recovery processes. Interestingly, Horticultural Waste also remained a consistent priority. The increased focus on agricultural residues like manures, sludges, and green manures suggests a pivot towards more readily available resources in the Irish agricultural sector. Meanwhile, the inclusion of grass and vegetable waste underscores a broader integration of diverse feedstocks to support a circular bioeconomy. Overall, these changes reflect a deeper understanding of resource utility and strategic alignment with sustainability goals.

Table 8-4. Results on the calibration of resources available in Ireland

Resources meeting 2 (April 2024)	Resources meeting 3 (October 2024)
Cattle slurry	Cattle slurry
Timber felling waste	Pig & poultry manure
Food waste	Dairy & Brewers sludge
Pig & poultry manure	Green manures & Cover crops
Horticultural waste	Horticultural waste
AD digestate	Timber felling waste
Dairy & Brewers sludge	Vegetable waste
Straw	Poultry ash
Poultry ash	Straw
By-products from meat production	Rushes & Gorse
Rushes & Gorse	Grass
Green manures & Cover crops	By-products from meat production

8.3.2 Recalibration of needs in the region

Similarly, the prioritisation of needs was discussed again in meeting 3 to re-calibrate them based on the opinion of the FAN members. There were a number of observed changes in the prioritisation of needs identified in the region (Table 4-5). The recalibration of needs demonstrates an evolving focus on enabling greater circularity and addressing specific infrastructural and technological gaps in the Irish bioeconomy. For example, Regional Funding for Shared Technology and Infrastructure was recalibrated as top priority in Meeting 3, reflecting a stronger emphasis on collaboration and pooled resources to overcome economic and logistical barriers. Making processes more circular was also highlighted as a priority, reinforcing the overarching goal of achieving a more sustainable bioeconomy.

Some additional needs highlighted by the FAN for the region included Green Biorefineries in light of their potential to valorise a range of biomasses.

Incinerators for Wood By-Product Ashes Generation moved down in priority while a need for a greater number of AD plants also decreased. There was no change in the prioritisation of the need for slurry separation technology, demonstrating its ongoing importance in managing agricultural waste and recovering valuable nutrients.

The emphasis on increased biomass utilisation and green biorefinery technology reflects a broader vision to diversify and maximise the value extracted from bio-resources. The reshuffling also highlights a balanced approach—maintaining focus on foundational technologies like slurry separation while advancing higher-value opportunities in line with evolving challenges and opportunities in Ireland’s bioeconomy.

Table 8-5. Results on the calibration of needs in the Irish region

Needs meeting 2	Needs meeting 3
Incinerators for wood by-product ashes generation	Regional funding for shared technology and infrastructure
Mulchers and chippers for processing wood by-products	Making processes more circular
Greater number of AD plants	Shared technology and infrastructure
Making processes more circular	Increased biomass utilisation
Slurry separation technology	Slurry separation technology
Root harvesting equipment	Greater number of AD plants
Increased biomass utilisation	Green biorefinery
Regional funding for shared technology and infrastructure	Mulchers and chippers for processing wood by-products
Shared technology and infrastructure	Incinerators for wood by-product ashes generation
	Root harvesting equipment

8.4 Section 3: Economic variables

8.4.1 Supply Value

The supply values of the various biomasses discussed by members of the Irish FAN indicate significant variation in base costs, reflecting their availability, production processes, and inherent nutrient content. Cattle slurry (€90/tonne) and pig & poultry manure (€85/tonne) were among the more valuable livestock-derived biomasses due to their nutrient-dense profiles, essential for improving soil fertility. Conversely, vegetable waste (€15/tonne) was deemed less valuable. Timber felling waste (€55/tonne) and green manures & cover crops (€55/tonne) were denoted to have intermediate value, reflecting their utility in soil enhancement but also their broader availability. Higher costs for materials like dairy brewers' sludge (€65/tonne) may be related to additional processing requirements. Overall, the variation in supply costs highlights a balance between demand for nutrient recycling and the logistics involved in sourcing and transporting these materials.

8.4.2 Subrogation Value

Bark remnants (€115/tonne) and bark ashes (€120/tonne) offer significant value as soil amendments as potential replacements of traditional synthetic fertilisers, enhancing fertility and carbon sequestration. Similarly, separated dairy cow manure (€100/tonne) and AD digestate-based fertilisers (€160/tonne) provide nutrient-rich organic fertilisers, promoting sustainable nutrient cycling. Fertilisers derived from woodchips, ashes, and biochar were deemed to have a subrogation value of €125/tonne, showing the potential to integrate forestry residues into soil management strategies. Meanwhile, heating materials from wood processing by-products (€150/tonne) and small-scale biogas production (€115/tonne) demonstrate the energy potential of biomass, supporting circular economy practices and reducing reliance on fossil fuels. These values underscore the role of FAN in aligning bio-based technologies with sustainability objectives in Ireland.

Table 8-6. Economic variables supply value and subrogation value of biomasses in the Irish region

Supply Value	Subrogation value
Cattle slurry €90/tonne	agronomic use of bark remnants €115/tonne
Pig & poultry manure €85/tonne	agronomic use of bark ashes €120 /tonne
Dairy Brewers sludge €65/tonne	Separated dairy cow manure €100/tonne
Green manures & Cover crops €55/tonne	AD digestate based fertilisers €160/tonne
Horticultural waste €35 /tonne	Fertilisers from woodchips, ashes and biochar €125/tonne
Timber felling waste €55 /tonne	Heating materials made from wood processing by-products €150 /tonne
Vegetable waste €15/tonne	Small scale biogas production from on-farm feedstock €115/tonne
Poultry ash €80/tonne	
Rushes & Gorse €30/tonne	

9 Polish FAN

9.1 Workshop details

Table 9-1. Details of workshop 3 in the Polish FAN

Venue	Hotel Ambassador Łódź + telephone contact
Date	07/11/2024
Format	Hybrid – In person and via telephone
Attendee number	9
Name of the event	IV Szczyt Polskich Grup Operacyjnych EPI 4th Summit of Polish EPI Operational Groups

9.2 Section 1: Debate over the BBTs and feasibility for their region.

During the first phase of the workshop, 10 BBTs were introduced by IUNG to the FAN members for debate. These were taken from lists generated from other EU Operational Groups and were subsequently discussed for their feasibility for the Polish RR. These BBTs are displayed in Table 9-2 below. Similar to the FANs in other regions, the list of 10 BBTs were sent to FAN members 1 week prior to the workshop in order for the members to become familiar with them. As common with the workshops held in all other RRs, each BBT was prioritised with a score from -5 to +5 according to the 5 criteria described in section 3.1 of this document.

Table 9-2. Description of BBTs selected for debate among FAN members for their suitability to the Polish region.

No.	BBT Code	BBT Description
1	QK1710379	Safe utilization of sewage sludge on agricultural land using torrefaction technology
2	TH02030925	The biochar addition effect to change the properties of compost
3	BioAnimalChar	Exploitation of remained agricultural biomass for the production of animal food supplements
4	COMPOST_INNO	Production and exploitation of compost from mixtures of agricultural waste
5	GO IMECO	Implementation of MTD for emissions control in the management and treatment of slurry
6		Small-scale farmer-led green biorefineries supporting farmer diversification into circular bioeconomy
7	IT45-Stabilized Litter	Stabilized litter for dairy cows: optimization of the use of litter derived from the solid fraction separated from manure
8	PROBEST	Progetto BioEconomia Salute e Territorio, economia circolare per la filiera legno-energia
9	PL93-GRIST	Organic grain production and processing of brewery residues into meal, using an innovative dehydration method
10	Not provided	Strengthening the potential of Polish apples by fully utilizing the fruit in the production of innovative eco-friendly products - developing fermented juice and compostable disposable packaging

9.2.1 Results on the prioritisation of BBTs in the region

Table 9-3. Summary of the prioritisation of each BBT for each key question in the Polish FAN

Questions	Is the BBT suitable for the available resources in the region?	Is the BBT suitable for the region's needs?	Does this BBT have the potential to develop a value chain?	Economic potential of the BBT for the region	Will the BBT benefit the environment and society in the region?	Weighting (average)
BBT 1	3.6	3.6	3.1	2.8	4.4	3.5
BBT 2	4.4	4.0	3.8	2.8	4.1	3.8
BBT 3	2.3	2.4	2.3	1.8	2.0	2.2
BBT 4	1.8	2.1	1.8	1.6	2.1	1.9
BBT 5	4.0	4.5	3.6	3.5	4.4	4
BBT 6	3.8	4.0	3.9	3.1	3.6	3.7
BBT 7	3.3	3.4	2.5	2.9	4.1	3.2
BBT 8	-0.1	-0.9	-0.1	-1.1	-1.1	-0.7
BBT 9	1.9	1.8	1.8	1.9	1.6	1.8
BBT10	4.6	3.8	4.0	3.1	3.1	3.7

The evaluation of the BBTs for the Polish region highlighted a number of key differences in their feasibility across the five key criteria. A number of BBTs received high scores demonstrating strong adaptability to the region's resources and needs. For example, BBT 5 - focusing on emissions control in slurry management received a score of 4.0. BBT2, which enhances composting practices with biochar, received a score of 3.8 aligning well with agricultural priorities. Meanwhile BBT6 received a score of 3.7 which focusses on supporting small-scale farmer-led biorefineries, and BBT10 scored 3.7 for innovative use of apples, reflect a strong alignment with regional needs for circular bioeconomy and eco-friendly innovation.

In contrast, BBT8 scored -0.7, centred on the wood-energy chain, faces significant challenges, potentially due to limited resource alignment or low regional demand for such applications. BBTs 3 and 4 scored moderately at 2.2 and 1.9 respectively, showing some potential but remaining less aligned to suitability in the region than other BBTs mentioned above. BBT9 and BBT4 showed limited alignment with the region compared to higher-ranked options, scoring 1.8 and 1.9 respectively. Overall, the analysis underscores the importance of aligning BBTs with regional resources, needs, and value chain potential while ensuring environmental and societal benefits.

9.3 Section 2: Recalibration of Needs and Resources for the region

9.3.1 Recalibration of resources in the region

Table 4-4 presents a list of biomass resources identified in the Polish region, initially outlined in a meeting held on 18/04/2024 and later revisited and recalibrated during a follow-up meeting on 30/09/2024. Interestingly, the rankings and inclusion of resources remained consistent across both meetings, reflecting an overall agreement on the relative importance and availability of these resources.

Table 9-4. Results on the calibration of resources available in Poland

Resources meeting 2 (18/04/2024)	Resources meeting 3 (30/09/2024)
1. Slurry separation	1. Slurry separation
2. Root harvesting equipment	2. Root harvesting equipment
3. Processing animal excrement into modern fertilizers: RENURE -Recovered Nitrogen from manure	3. Processing animal excrement into modern fertilizers: RENURE -Recovered Nitrogen from manure
4. Processing of agri-food waste,	4. Processing of agri-food waste,
5. Biochar production	5. Biochar production
6. Pellet from agricultural waste	6. Pellet from agricultural waste

9.3.2 Recalibration of needs in the region

There were a number of observed changes in the prioritisation of needs identified in the region between the first and second meetings (**Error! Reference source not found.**). The need for improved machinery to collect wood biomass (branches, needles/leaves) after thinning and felling increased in priority, moving from rank 3 to 5, suggesting a growing emphasis on optimising forestry waste management to support bio-based technologies like biomass energy or compost production. Similarly, the biomass coaling installation also saw an increase in importance (rank 4 to 5), reflecting heightened interest in technologies for carbon-rich biomass products.

On the other hand, the priority for machines to process hemp straw for fibre slightly decreased (rank 3 to 2). Meanwhile, the introduction of technology to produce RENURE (Recovered Nitrogen from Manure) and the mobile pellet production machine maintained their rankings at 8 and 4, respectively. This consistency suggests these technologies remain important but without immediate urgency relative to the higher prioritised needs.

These shifts underscore an increased focus on forestry resource optimisation and bio-based carbon production while balancing interest in agricultural and energy technologies.

Table 9-5. Results on the calibration of needs in the Polish region

Identified needs for the Polish region	final ranking	initial ranking	difference
Improved machinery to collect branches, needles/leaves, and other wood-biomass after thinning and felling.	5	3	↑
Machines to process hemp straw to make fibre.	2	3	↓
Introduction of technology to produce RENURE	8	8	↔
Introduction of biomass coaling installation	5	4	↑
Mobile pellet production machine	4	4	↔

9.4 Section 3: Economic variables

9.4.1 Supply Value

The supply values of the biomasses reflect their economic potential and roles in the Polish bioeconomy. Biochar (€2.28/kg) has the highest value, driven by its versatile applications in soil enhancement, carbon sequestration, and filtration, though its cost may limit widespread adoption. Biofertiliser (€1.2/kg) offers a balance of scalability and economic viability, making it a strong candidate for nutrient recycling in agriculture. In contrast, compost from organic effluents (€0.01/kg) was deemed to have a low value due to its abundance and simpler production but remains essential for soil health and waste management. This gradient highlights biochar and biofertiliser as high-value products, while compost underpins sustainable agricultural practices.

9.4.2 Subrogation Value

In terms of subrogation value, replacement costs of bio-based products relative to traditional fertilisers, members of the Polish Fan were not able to provide information on this aspect of the workshop.

Table 9-6. Economic variables supply value and subrogation value of biomasses in the Polish region

Supply Value	Subrogation value
Biomass 1- Biochar 2.28€/kg	Bio-based Product 1- Organic biomass waste: € €/kg
Biomass 2- Biofertiliser: 1,2€/kg	Bio-based Product 2 – Pruning waste: €/kg
Biomass 3- Compost from organic effluents: 0.01€/kg	Bio-based Product 3 – Waste Treatment €/kg
	Bio-based Product 4- Herbaceous biomass €/kg

10 Conclusion

This report offers a comprehensive overview of the validation and prioritisation of BBTs across the six representative regions within the BBioNets consortium. Through detailed workshops and collaborative discussions, the findings highlight the alignment of prioritised BBTs with regional resources, needs, and economic contexts. The recalibration of needs and resources highlight the dynamic nature of regional priorities and the importance of adapting strategies to promote circular bioeconomy processes effectively.

Examples of highly prioritised BBTs in each region included:

- In **Italy**, technologies focusing on the agronomic use of bark and pruning residues to enhance soil organic carbon and reduce dependence on fossil-derived peat were highly prioritised.
- In the **Andalusian** region of **Spain**, olive-related technologies dominated, including olive by-product recovery for composting and biochar production, reflecting the region's agricultural profile.
- In **Greece**, olive mill by-product recovery (e.g., composting) and composting technologies were strongly aligned with the region's agricultural needs.
- In the **Czech Republic**, biogas systems and biochar-enhanced compost were validated as the most suitable technologies for the region.
- In **Ireland**, composting agricultural residues and technologies focusing on soil health and mixed biomass use for energy and soil enhancement were prioritised.
- In **Poland**, technologies addressing emissions control in slurry management and biochar-enhanced compost were strongly aligned with regional needs.

Examples of the recalibration of needs in each representative region included:

- In **Italy**, investment resources and projects focusing on collaboration emerged as key priorities. A notable shift occurred towards sustainable materials, such as thermoplastic starch for biodegradable products.
- In the **Andalusian** region of **Spain**, Policies to address the lack of technical and financial support gained prominence. Awareness of circular bioeconomy concepts and the added value of bio-products were emphasised.
- In **Greece**, increasing farmer education, access to technology, and piloting schemes emerged as critical needs. Inter-sectoral collaboration was slightly deprioritised.
- In the **Czech Republic**, developing value chains and innovative biomass utilisation were prioritised to strengthen regional bioeconomy efforts.
- In **Ireland**, shared infrastructure and funding for collaborative projects were key needs identified during recalibration.
- In **Poland**, Forestry resource optimisation and enhancing carbon-rich biomass production became higher priorities.

Examples of economic insights in each region included:

- In **Italy**, Compost and biochar were identified as valuable bio-based products, with a high focus on cost-effective and regionally adapted solutions.
- In the **Andalusian** region of **Spain**, Olive pits and pruning residues had high supply and subrogation values, supporting their potential for biofuels and fertiliser alternatives.
- In **Greece**, Olive mill waste, and manure were identified as cost-effective resources, with biochar and bioenergy showing strong subrogation value for sustainability applications.
- In the **Czech Republic**, fast-growing woody plants had a high supply value, while the high subrogation value of producing alfalfa forage (SeCoPPA) at €177/tonne corresponds to their potential in a sustainable energy source from agriculture.
- In **Ireland**, Cattle slurry (€90/tonne) and pig & poultry manure (€85/tonne) were among the more valuable livestock-derived biomasses due to their nutrient-dense profiles. While bark remnants (€115/tonne) and bark ashes (€120/tonne) offer significant value as soil amendments
- In **Poland**, biochar (€2.28/kg) had a high supply value due to versatile applications in soil enhancement and carbon sequestration.

Document information

Title BBioNets - Creation and promotion of Forest and Agriculture Networks to boost Bio-Based Technologies adoption and Value Chain development (GA No 101133904)

Start - end date 1/11/2023 – 31/10/2026 (36 months)

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Programme Horizon Europe – Cluster 6

Funding 1,998,636.20 €

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Project overview BBioNets will constitute a thematic network that will rely on, promote, and further advance the work carried out by EIP AGRI Operational Groups (OGs) with respect to **management and/or processing of agricultural and forest biomass with Bio-Based Technologies (BBTs)**. The project will set up 6 regional Forest and Agriculture Networks - FANs (IE, ES, IT, GR, PL, CZ) that will identify local needs, prioritise specific BBTs and share BBT knowledge ready for practice to farmers and foresters, boosting the (re)definition of value chains, stimulating cross-fertilisation beyond borders, and bringing Europe to the forefront of farming, forestry, and bioeconomy with economically viable and sustainable practices.

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